

TEACHING ENGLISH TO CHILDREN THROUGH FAIRY TALES

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Annotation: This guide on methodology explores the incorporation of fairy tales in foreign language instruction. Employing fairy tales in the educational setting is designed to enhance the effectiveness of student engagement and further foster the development of a child's linguistic proficiency.

This resource can prove beneficial for educators in supplementary education, preschool teachers, and parents of young children.

Key words: fairy tale, game situation, educational and cognitive activity, interest, game, memory.

Teaching communication in a foreign language to children who haven't fully mastered communication skills in their native language is a challenging and crucial task. Developing a love for a subject at this age is closely tied to the psychological comfort, joy, and readiness for communication that a teacher cultivates in the classroom. One effective method to engage and motivate preschoolers is through fairy tale therapy.

Fairy tale therapy utilizes the narrative structure to integrate personality, foster creativity, expand consciousness, and enhance interaction with the outside world. A fairy tale captivates, amuses, and stimulates thinking, making the learning process visual and aiding in the enactment of dialogues—a effective and straightforward way to convey information in a form accessible to children. [1]

The role of English fairy tales in language acquisition is significant. Recognizing that children absorb information best through play, fairy tales offer a playful approach to learning—a universal tool that models proper behavior, addresses psychological issues, and more. Fairy tales, as ancient creations, effortlessly transcend linguistic boundaries and remain relevant across cultures for centuries.

The concise and expressive nature of fairy tales, coupled with the narrator's simple yet engaging delivery, allows for the conveyance of not only a person's characteristic qualities but also their deepest, most hidden features. The versatility of fairy tales and the various. [2]

Approaches to working with them enable teachers to incorporate fairy tale therapy into aesthetic education. For instance, the analytical approach and the creation of a fairy tale can be recommended for use in artistic and speech activities, music classes (such as listening to and analyzing a musical fairy tale), and visual arts classes (e.g., drawing a favorite character from a fairy tale). Rewriting a fairy tale can be applied in artistic activities, daily life, and during celebrations.

The use of fairy tales in the classroom aims to enhance the effectiveness of preschool education. The widespread integration of fairy tales contributes to the development of linguistic competence, with the content of these texts helping expand the active vocabulary. Dramatizing fairy tales fosters psychological comfort in the classroom, alleviating negative emotions and creating a friendly atmosphere of communication within the group. Fairytale therapy is also a significant tool for moral education, aiding in the development of communicative competence among preschoolers and increasing their interest in the subject of "English." [3]

In English classes, the use of fairy tales exposes children to diverse characters, traditions, and allows for comparisons with Russian fairy tales. Exploring similarities and differences in plots provides insights into distinct cultures while revealing universal themes. Through fairy tales, teachers can develop a wide range of skills and abilities, teach prediction, and facilitate discussions about content. Preschoolers learn to identify the emotional states of fairy-tale characters depicted in pictures and retell the tales. For these young learners, even the simplest fairy tales familiar from infancy

must be adapted. Elements of puppet therapy, such as a toy monkey narrating stories or dolls presenting riddles, are also incorporated.

At the initial stage, fairy tales play a crucial role in teaching phonetics and vocabulary. Learning with fairy-tale characters becomes both entertaining and educational, as the characters exhibit diverse personalities. By embodying characters from childhood, students overcome the speech barrier, as any mistakes made are attributed to the fairy-tale characters. Meanwhile, the consistent use of epithets, comparisons, and set expressions in specific places within the text, along with lexical and syntactic variations, enriches students' vocabulary and facilitates the comprehension and assimilation of grammatical material. Memorizing rhymed texts, creating illustrations, staging fairy tales for parents and celebrations all contribute to the development of students' communicative competence and heighten their interest in the foreign language subject. [4]

When teaching a foreign language to young learners, selecting an appropriate content foundation becomes a crucial consideration. The distinctive qualities of fairy tales make them an ideal and meaningful basis for learning, surpassing other literary genres due to their incorporation of fiction and fantastical elements.

For preschoolers, engaging with a fairy tale goes beyond a mere narrative; they perceive fantastic characters as real, sympathizing and experiencing the tale's events. This ability for empathy and imagination nurtures independent creativity and imaginative thinking. The inherent fiction in fairy tales provides ample room for children to express their vivid imaginations. Working with fairy tales allows teachers to not only draw from children's experiences but also tap into their imaginative capacities, thereby expanding the scope of communication content.

A fairy tale, fundamentally poetic fiction, maintains a unique connection with reality, shaping its ideological content, plot, characters, narrative details, and language. While fantasy is a central aspect, every fairy tale, no matter how fantastical, paints realistic pictures of folk life. Beneath the surface of the adventures lie human destinies, and the conflicts mirror complex societal relationships. Authors subtly convey profound messages about choosing an honest path, the challenges of

loneliness, the joys of friendship, the impact of fear on international relations, and the significance of sincerity and trust for global peace and happiness. Although the depiction is in a special, fantastical form understandable to children, the themes and moral values remain mature and genuine.

Now, let's explore the educational possibilities that a fairy tale offers as a meaningful foundation for learning and how it addresses educational objectives.

During the early stages of instruction, the developmental aspect takes precedence as foundational abilities are laid and initial development occurs. A fairy tale proves to be an excellent resource for addressing developmental goals.[5]

A crucial aim of the developmental aspect is the establishment of a motivational-need block, especially during the initial learning period when teachers strive to instill a stable motivation for learning a foreign language. The captivating content of a fairy tale greatly contributes to creating motivation for mastering the foreign language.

A foreign language allows children to delve into the captivating plots of fairy tales from other cultures, introducing them to the folk heroes of the story's origin. The lesson plan, centered around a fairy tale, immediately captures children's attention. Learning a foreign language through a fairy tale transforms the educational process into an exciting and eagerly anticipated endeavor for the child. It enables teachers to inspire children to actively participate in their learning, making them willing partners in the quest for knowledge and fostering a positive attitude toward the educational journey.[6]

In the older preschool age, children develop various communication skills, including personal, personal-role, business, and status communication. A fairy tale in a foreign language naturally stimulates the need for communication in children, aligning with their interests and age-appropriate needs.

The educational potential of a fairy tale in a foreign language is substantial. It serves as an unobtrusive educational tool, revealing to children the intricacies of human relationships, emotions, and a rich moral landscape—covering aspects such as

kindness, respect, sympathy, camaraderie, justice, responsiveness, and mutual understanding.[7]

Early exposure to fairy tales in a foreign language nurtures a genuine interest in the lives of people from other countries. A positive emotional connection with a foreign language fairy tale helps prevent the emergence of mistrust and hostility often seen in adults reacting to the unfamiliar. At this age, children naturally develop a cognitive interest in the culture of the language they are studying, and fairy tales serve as a rich source for acquiring this knowledge. Education centered around fairy tales allows for the exploration of elements of a national culture expressed in the literary language standard of that nation. The linguistic and cultural aspects are clearly expressed in fairy tales, forming an integral component of the learning content that provides "background" knowledge for effective communication in a foreign language.

When employing a fairy tale as a meaningful foundation for learning, cognitive interest in the culture of the language being studied is realized through the acquisition of knowledge: about the culture of the country where the language originated (including history, geography, peer lifestyles, traditions, interests, music, painting, symbolism, clothing, holidays, and hobbies); about corresponding elements of world culture; and about the relationship between foreign language culture and one's native culture.[8]

A fairy tale, as a meaningful foundation for teaching, proves effective in addressing educational goals. Learning to speak based on a fairy tale shapes children's understanding of a foreign language as a medium for interpersonal communication equivalent to their native language. In terms of content, a fairy tale is an excellent tool for organizing the process of acquiring various foreign language communication skills.

When utilizing a fairy tale as a meaningful foundation for learning, the development of speaking skills is directed toward fostering communicative readiness and cultivating an attitude toward using a foreign language for communication. A fairy tale, as a meaningful foundation for teaching speaking, encourages students to

actively engage in communication and co-creation. Playful role-playing communication scenarios can be constructed on the meaningful foundation of a fairy tale.

CONCLUSION

Absolutely, an English fairy tale possesses the enchanting ability not only to captivate readers but also, owing to its structure, to instruct various aspects of speech activity and aid in overcoming cultural barriers. In the contemporary educational landscape, incorporating fairy tales and a corresponding set of exercises into English lessons offers a versatile solution to numerous educational challenges.

In summary, it is crucial to recognize the diversity among children, as each individual requires a unique approach and key to unlock their potential. One child may thrive in composing and narrating stories, while another is more kinetic and benefits from movement; a third may enjoy hands-on activities, and a fourth may have a passion for drawing. By integrating diverse techniques of fairy tale therapy within aesthetic education, it becomes possible to guide each child through a spectrum of situations, emotions, and feelings—parallel to real-life experiences. This approach significantly broadens a child's worldview, enhances their interaction with the world and others, teaches them to appreciate the beauty in their surroundings, and instills confidence in sharing their creativity and the elements of beauty that reflect their inner world with the world at large.

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